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**Environmentally-friendly processing of
thermosets by two-stage sequential aza-Michael
addition and free-radical polymerization of
amine-acrylate mixtures.**

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Glossary

α	Acrylate group conversion
f_w	Amine functionality
α_{gel}	Conversion of acrylate/methacrylate groups at gelation
A	Absorbance
BENP	Benzophenone
BGDA	Bisphenol A glycerolate (1 glycerol/phenol) diacrylate
BGDMA	Bisphenol A glycerolate (1 glycerol/phenol)
BPOX	Benzoyl peroxide
CED	Cohesive energy density
DETA	Diethylenetriamine
DMA	dynamic mechanical analysis
DMPA	Dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone
DSC	differential scanning calorimetry
E'	Storage modulus
E''	Losses modulus
HDDA	1,6- Hexanediol diacrylate
HPB	Hyperbranched polymer
JEFF	Jeffamine D-2320 Polyetheramine
LPFG	Poly (ethyleneimine) Lupasol FG
MEKP	Methyl ethyl ketone peroxide
OCO	Cobalt (II) octoate 0.5% solution in phthalate
r	stoichiometric ratio acrylate groups/reactive amine hydrogens
$T_{5\%}$	Decomposition temperature for a mass loss of 5%
$\tan \delta$	The lag between tension and deformation waves

TEGDMA	Triethylene glycol- dimethacrylate
T_g	Glass transition temperature
$T_{g,0}$	Glass temperature of the amorphous thermoset
$T_{g,\infty}$	Glass temperature of the completely cured thermoset
$T_{g,gel}$	Glass temperature of the thermoset at the gel point
TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
TMA	Thermomechanical analysis
T_{max}	Maximum degradation temperatures
TMPTA	Trimethylolpropane tricarylate
T_{use}	Use temperature
$W_{amine}/W_{acrylate}$	The ratio of amine mass and acrylate mass

Summary

This project aims to present a novel method to prepare and characterize thermosets based on aza-Michael and radical photopolymerization dual curing of off-stoichiometric amine-acrylate formulations with custom-tailored properties after the first curing stage and of the final material. In the first stage, amino and acrylate groups react through an aza-Michael mechanism to form a partially reacted material. This reactive process proceeds at room temperature and may be catalyzed by the tertiary amines contained in the reagents or formed by the reaction of a primary amine or secondary amine with two or one equivalents of the acceptor respectively. In the second stage, the photoinitiated free radical polymerization of the excess of acrylic groups embedded within the material formed in the first stage results in a crosslinked network. The tertiary amines present in the reaction medium may also act as oxygen scavengers or as co-initiator when a type II photoinitiator is used during the second curing stage. To perform the tests, mixtures of acrylates of different functionality and structure, a simple or hyperbranched amine, and a type I photoinitiator have been used as reference materials. Methacrylates, a type II photoinitiator, and a thermal free-radical initiator have also been tested for comparison purposes. The kinetics of aza-Michael addition and the conversion reached at the end of the two stages have been studied by FTIR spectroscopy and the gelation by thermomechanical analysis (TMA). The materials obtained have been characterized by calorimetry differential scanning (DSC) and dynamomechanical analysis (DMA).

The methodology used in this thesis project is simple, versatile, environmentally friendly and makes it possible to fine-tune the properties of both the intermediate and final materials. By controlling the stoichiometric amine/acrylate ratio in the formulation and the amine functionality, a broad range of glass transition temperatures can be achieved, from -38°C to 40°C in the intermediate stage and from -5°C to 150°C at the end of the second curing stage. Likewise, ungelled or gelled materials can be obtained after the first curing stage. All materials are stable after aza-Michael addition and can be safely stored before further application in a second step.

The first chapter exposes the basic principles of cross-linked network formation, especially when free-radical polymerization is involved. Moreover, the addition of a nucleophilic to an α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compound (known as Michael reaction) and the use of hyperbranched polymers containing amines as a nitrogen donor in the Michael addition is described. The second chapter presents the materials used in this project, such as acrylates and methacrylates reactive monomers, reagent-containing amines, and the catalytic systems (initiators) as the different methods of characterization utilized and sample preparation description.

The third chapter is completely dedicated to the research results and discussion. First, the effect of the amine (multifunctional or difunctional) stoichiometric proportion variation on a mixture of diacrylates was analyzed to obtain thermoset by dual curing aza-Michael reaction/free radical photopolymerization. Subsequently, it was evaluated the influence of acrylate arrangement on the structure-property relationships of poly(amino ester)-poly(acrylate)s thermosets obtained by the same process of dual curing. Then, the use of methacrylate monomers was studied when this was introduced (in combination with acrylate monomers) in the preparation of formulations. Finally, it was analyzed and compared the use of type II photoinitiators on mixtures of diacrylate/multifunctional amine with type I photoinitiators and the use of thermal initiators as a solution to arrive at the areas in which the UV radiation cannot reach.

1. Introduction

1.1 Thermosets

Thermosets are defined as the formation of a cross-linked polymer network by a chemical reaction called curing reaction of diverse monomers or oligomers, where at least one of them has three or more reactive groups per molecule. Since the polymer network is produced irreversibly, a thermosetting material is synthesized to produce the final material with the desired shape [1].

Crosslinking can occur by free-radical chain polymerization, polycondensation, and polyaddition of multifunctional monomers and oligomers. Examples include:

- Free radical polymerization of diallyl phthalate DAP and copolymerization of unsaturated polyesters.
- Polycondensation of formaldehyde with phenols (phenolic resin), urea (urea-formaldehyde), or melamine (melamine-formaldehyde) or formation of polyimide thermosets.
- Polycondensation of epoxides with carboxylic acids or multifunctional amines (epoxy resin) or of isocyanates with multifunctional alcohols (polyurethane).
- Polyaddition of epoxides with acid anhydrides with basic catalysis or base or acid-catalyzed homopolymerization of epoxides.

During the processing of thermosetting polymers, dramatic changes in the properties of the system occur. The curing process starts from a soluble phase formed by low molecular weight monomers, as seen in Figure 1.1-a. Then the reaction progresses and begins the chain growth, with increasing degree of branching, as seen in Figure 1.1-b, with increasing molecular weight but still having a liquid-like behavior. As the reaction proceeds, the increasing degree of branching and inter-molecular connection leads to the formation of a polymer molecule of infinite size percolating the system, as seen in Figure 1.1-c. This sudden and irreversible transformation is called gelation and marks the first appearance of the infinite network. Beyond this point, the system is no more fully liquid-like and becomes gradually insoluble as the crosslinking process advances until the entire material forms part of the three-dimensional network or gel, Figure 1.1-d, with a substantial increase in cross-link density, glass transition temperature, and ultimate physical properties [2]. The majority of thermosetting materials are amorphous since there is no possibility of ordering the reticular structure due to the restrictions imposed by crosslinks.

Gelation is characteristic of thermosets, and it is of foremost significance. Gelation is critical from a processing standpoint since the polymer does not flow and is no longer processable beyond this point. Gelation does not inhibit the curing process and cannot be detected by techniques sensitive solely to the chemical reaction, such as differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and only can be detected by techniques sensitive to the mechanical stability of the material, as thermomechanical analysis (TMA) and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), among others.

Figure 1.1: Two-dimensional representation of curing a thermoset polymer [2].

A relevant characteristic of polymers in general and in particular of crosslinking, thermosetting polymers is their glass transition temperature T_g . Below this temperature, the polymer molecules do not have enough energy and available free volume to permit segmental mobility, and the system is virtually frozen in a glassy state, which is a non-equilibrium state from a thermodynamic point of view. Above, the polymer molecules are in equilibrium, liquid or rubbery, and have enough mobility to permit segmental rearrangements. During curing of a thermosetting system, the T_g of the system increases due to chain growth and branching, leading to increased molecular weight and reduced mobility, and crosslinking, which further restricts chain mobility.

Another physical phenomenon that may occur during the curing process is the vitrification of the material. This transformation from a viscous liquid or elastic gel to a glass occurs when the glass transition temperature T_g of these growing chains becomes coincidental with the curing temperature. Further curing in the glassy state is extremely slow, and vitrification abruptly stops curing. Vitrification is a reversible phenomenon, and the curing process may be completed by heating to devitrify the partially cured thermoset. Most thermosetting polymers are formulated and selected to their transition temperature T_g that is higher than use temperature T_{use} .

There are three types of the glass temperature control process: The glass temperature of the amorphous thermosetting material $T_{G,0}$ (crystalline monomers are always processed at temperatures above their melting temperatures; oligomers are amorphous at these temperatures), the glass temperature of the thermoset at the gel point $T_{G,gel}$ and the glass temperature of the completely cured thermoset $T_{G,\infty}$.

Four curing regions can be distinguished according to the position of the hardening temperature T_h relative to the position of these three glass temperatures [3], as shown in Figure 1.2.

- (1) $T_h < T_{G,0}$: the thermosetting material remains in the glassy state during the whole experimental time (sol glass); there is no cross-linking and curing.

- (2) $T_{G,0} < T_h < T_{G,gel}$: thermosetting materials convert into prepolymers with increasing time. Prepolymers are liquid at low curing temperatures but vitrify with increasing reaction (increasing polymer concentration and higher molar mass).
- (3) $T_{G,gel} < T_h < T_{G,\infty}$: the polymerization continues to the gel point where a cross-linked gel is formed in a sol for the first time. The lower the curing temperature, the earlier the gel-sol mixture solidifies to glass. At high curing temperatures, polymer segments remain mobile. The gel-sol mixture continues to react. Finally, a gel glass is formed that consists of a completely cross-linked polymer.
- (4) $T_{G,\infty} < T_h$: the gel point is rapidly surpassed. However, the gel can only exist as an elastomer since it is above the glass temperature $T_{G,\infty}$ of the fully cured thermoset. A sol-gel elastomer is formed first and later, after a complete chemical reaction, a gel elastomer. If the system is maintained for too long at high temperatures, degradation leads to chain scission and secondary crosslinking. The gel elastomer is increasingly cross-linked. It finally becomes a glass that starts to degrade.

Figure 1.2: Time-temperature-transformation (TTT) diagram. The line G_0 indicates the onset of gelation at temperatures above $T_{G,0}$. Vitrification starts above the line V_0 . Full cure is obtained at temperatures above the line C_∞ .

The cross-linking of thermosetting materials proceeds at random; it commands the structure of networks and reduces the mobility of chain segments. Diffusion becomes increasingly difficult, and some functional groups do not find reactive partners during the normal course of the reaction. However, these residual groups can undergo after-reactions. Atmospheric agents (water, oxygen, etc.) can attack unreacted functional groups of thermosets and reduce their weather-ability. Some special-purpose thermosetting materials can thus be cross-linked only via end groups. An example is so-called vinyl ester resin which is not vinyl ester but difunctional macro monomers with long residues between (meth) acryl end groups.

1.2 Photo and thermal curing processes technologies

Photo curing processes use ultra-violet (UV) light, visible light, electron beam (EB) or laser to start photochemical and chemical reactions in organic materials (monomers, oligomers, prepolymers, polymers), mostly through a photo-induced polymerization reaction. This photo-induced reaction occurs when the radicals are generated by ultraviolet and visible light irradiation. In general, light absorption results in radical production by either of two pathways: some compound in the system undergoes excitation by energy absorption and subsequent decomposition into radicals, some compound undergoes excitation, and the excited species interacts with a second compound (by either energy transfer or redox reaction) to form radicals derived from the latter and/or former compound(s). The photosensitizer is the term used to refer to any substance that either increases the rate of photoinitiated polymerization or shifts the wavelength at which polymerization occurs. In the case of radical production by thermal energy, a radical initiator (peroxide, hydro-peroxide or aza compound) capable of decomposing to form radicals and initiate polymerization is required. Furthermore, adding a promoter in order to the thermal curing process is conducted at a lower temperature; a promoter reduces the initiator forming a radical, which also triggers the thermal crosslinking process. They are commonly used as promoters, aromatic tertiary amines or cobalt salts.

UV-curing offers significant practical advantages over the usual thermal curing process [4], e.g., are rapid through-cure, room temperature treatment and low energy requirements. Radical production and polymerization can be spatially directed (i.e., confined to particular regions) and turned on or off simply by switching the light source. Additionally, the initiation rates can be controlled by combining the source or radicals, light intensity, and temperature. Photochemical polymerization has found applications in decorative and protective coating and inks for metal, paper, wood, and plastics; in photolithography for producing integrated and printed circuits; and curing in dental materials. Many of these applications involve a combination of polymerization and crosslinking. Crosslinking is often achieved by using monomers with two or more double bonds per molecule. Acrylate systems are the most common, although unsaturated polyester and styrene systems are also employed. Photopolymerization is also of special interest in applications where economic and/or environmental considerations require the use of solvent-free systems. The significant drawback to Photopolymerization is that the penetration through the thickness of the material is low, limiting use to the surface-type application.

The radical photopolymerization of multifunctional monomers and oligomers is very fast and generally sensitive to the presence of oxygen. Usual monomers and oligomers are based on acrylates, for example, hexanediol diacrylate (HDDA), tripropyleneglycol diacrylate (TPGDA), trimethylolpropane triacrylate (TMPTA), Isobornyl acrylate, Polyester diacrylate and Epoxy diacrylate. Sometimes, they possess a strong odor and exhibit skin-irritating properties. Unsaturated polyester resins dissolved in styrene are well known in curing glass-reinforced materials.

A conventional radical polymerization terminates when the reactive intermediates are destroyed or inactive through bimolecular reactions [5]. The radical generation is irreversible without any possibility of controlling the final properties of the polymer formed, such as the number average of molecular weight M_n and the molecular weight distribution (MWD). The different steps of a radical photopolymerization reaction are shown in Figure 1.3. Under light irradiation of the photoinitiator (PI), initiating radicals R^* are created. Then they react with the monomer M to give the first macroradical. The reaction propagation takes place through the subsequent addition of monomer units to the growing macroradical. The last step is the mono or bimolecular termination

reaction, depending on the experimental conditions. The bimolecular termination occurs through the recombination of two polymer chains and disproportionation. The monomolecular termination arises when the photopolymerizable resin becomes so viscous or rigid that the diffusion or the remaining monomer close to the reactive centers is prevented. Therefore, the reactive centers are possibly trapped within the polymeric medium, and consequently, the conversion of the monomer is lower than 100%.

Figure 1.3: Different steps of radical photopolymerization reaction.

During the reaction, consumption of the monomer double bonds occurs. The photopolymerization profile (or the conversion-time curve) has a characteristic S-shape (as shown in Figure 1.4) and can be divided into three different regimes:

- (1) In the early stages after the light illumination, the excited states and the reactive species react with the inhibitors such as oxygen and stabilizers leading to an induction period during which the polymerization hardly starts.
- (2) When all the inhibitors (for example, oxygen) are consumed, the reactive species react with the monomer and lead to the formation of macroradicals that propagate; thus, the polymerization rate rapidly increases to reach a maximum value.
- (3) The medium becomes more and more solid, and the polymerization reaction slows down until a plateau is reached for the conversion.

Figure 1.4: Typical time evolution of the radical photopolymerization reaction of an acrylate.

As mentioned at the beginning, the presence of oxygen leads to several detrimental effects in radical photopolymerization, for example, the presence of an induction period, the decrease of the polymerization rate and the final conversion, the reduction of the polymer chain length, and the formation of a tacky surface on the coating. Oxygen inhibition significantly affects the top surface layer and the network structure of the final polymer material in terms of physical properties, as confirmed by a recent investigation [6]. In films up to 100 μm , oxygen decreases the reaction rate

and spatial anisotropy of the polymer yield [7]. Many efforts have been made to overcome oxygen inhibition by using various strategies. Among the main strategies for eliminating oxygen inhibition, it can be appointed [8]:

- (1) Curing in an oxygen-free atmosphere purging nitrogen or CO₂ [9].
- (2) Increasing the photoinitiator content.
- (3) Increasing the duration and the intensity of light exposure.
- (4) Addition of oxygen scavengers.
- (5) Hydrogen donors.

The last strategy is schematized in Figure 1.5. It can be observed that the hydrogen donor (*DH*) provides a hydrogen atom limiting the already formed alkylperoxyl radical. While the alkylperoxyl radical does not readily react with acrylate monomers, the newly formed radical (*D*^{*}) can react with monomers and thus reinitiate polymerization. Although donor hydrogen is schematically represented donating one hydrogen atom, molecules that donate multiple hydrogens are also very common, allowing kinetic chain length to remain high despite oxygen inhibition.

Figure 1.5: chain transfer by Hydrogen donors [8].

As hydrogen donor primary, secondary and tertiary amines can be used; however, tertiary amines are ideal due to lower volatility and higher reactivity. Donation of hydrogen occurs from the carbon adjacent to nitrogen, providing alkyl radical stabilized in an anticoplanar arrangement with the lone pair orbital on nitrogen permitting sharing of π -electrons [10]. In the mentioned reaction, a hydroperoxide is formed, and the newly formed aminoalkyl radical can react with acrylate monomers to reinitiate polymerization. The aminoalkyl radical can alternatively react with an oxygen molecule to provide an aminoalkylperoxide radical (as shown in Figure 1.6).

The range of monomers and oligomers available for the preparation of thermosets via photopolymerization has been largely expanded; for example, epoxides and vinyl ethers (VEs) are widely used and are known to give coatings with high thermal capability, excellent adhesion, good chemical resistance, and environmentally friendly character [11]. VEs (e.g., diethyleneglycol divinyl ether) polymerize faster than epoxides (e.g., cycloaliphatic diepoxide) [12]. Cyclic ethers such as oxetanes can be alternatives to epoxides for getting faster curing speeds in industrial lines [13]–[15]. A proper selection of cationic monomers with readily abstractable hydrogen atoms helps the design of high-performance systems. Recent developments include hybrid monomers (epoxide-vinyl ethers, epoxide-propenyl ethers, epoxide and acetals) and monomers bearing functional groups [16].

Figure 1.6: Role of amines in reducing oxygen inhibition [10].

The use of anionic photopolymerization is an almost unknown field in radiation curing. Indeed, owing to the high reactivity of the propagation species (seen in Figure 1.7), the anionic reaction has to be carried out in the absence of impurities and compounds sensitive to nucleophiles. Polycyanoacrylates are obtained according to this process [17], [18] Metallocenophanes such as silicon-bridged (1)ferrocenophanes [19] have also been reported to be candidates for such a reaction. This led to a class of metallopolymers (exhibiting a controlled response to redox stimuli, an etch resistance to plasma, high refractive indices, a precursor behavior to nanostructured magnetic ceramics, or catalysts of carbon nanotube growth). Thiol-ene photopolymerization is also interesting since it shows some fascinating features: very fast process, low or even no oxygen inhibition effect, and formation of highly cross-linked networks with good adhesion, reduced shrinkage and stress, and improved physical and mechanical properties. Thiol-ene photopolymerization is based on a stoichiometric reaction of multifunctional olefins and thiols, for example, thiol-vinyl ether, thiol-allyl ether, thiol-acrylate, thiol-yne, or thiol-allyl ether-acrylate [20].

Figure 1.7: The propagation species of anionic photopolymerization.

The principal issue of the photo curing processes is the presence of some shadow areas in large three-dimensional objects, which can hardly be reached by UV radiation and will remain uncured. To overcome this problem, dual-cure systems combining UV irradiation and thermal treatment have been developed [21]. These systems contain two reactive functions: a UV-curable functional group (usually an acrylate double bond) and a thermally curable functional group (usually an isocyanate associated with a polyol). The acrylate is first cured on light exposure, and the subsequent dark reaction of the isocyanates with the hydroxyl groups of the acrylates allows full

curing of the coating, thereby producing a tack-free film. A combination of thermal and UV-induced polymerization was studied to prepare acrylate-oxetane 1:1 molar systems [22]. The mixture was first subjected to thermal radical polymerization and successively a cationic UV induced ring-opening polymerization of oxetanes monomer. Another example of a dual photo-thermal curing system is represented by the *in situ* thioether groups by a thiol-ene reaction on allyl terminated hyperbranched polyester. This reaction takes place by photoirradiation at the beginning of the curing process, which transforms thioether moieties into trialkylsulfonium groups by reacting with activated epoxy groups. However, these sulfonium salts are inactive under UV irradiation, but they can be activated thermally, leading to highly crosslinked networks [22]. In the same context, the preparation of organic-inorganic hybrid dual cure has been reported, where the first stage is the radical-cationically photopolymerization followed subsequently by a hydrolysis-condensation (sol-gel process) [23]. One of the main advantages of those systems is that the oxygen inhibition of free-radical polymerization is greatly reduced, obtaining higher conversion grades. Besides, another kind of dual curing of the hybrid system was proposed by [24], in which was developed a hybrid network based on thiol-ene/thiol-epoxy to counteract the high shrinkage and stress produced by the chain polymerization of the acrylate or vinyl ether networks.

1.3 Michael Reaction

The Michael addition reaction, commonly called conjugate addition, refers to the base-catalyzed addition of a nucleophile, also called ‘Michael donor’ to an activated α,β -unsaturated carbonyl-containing compound, the ‘Michael acceptor’ [25]. However, through the years, it has been possible to include this reaction other a broad range of acceptors and non-carbon donors or non-enolate nucleophiles such as amines and thiols. α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds, which own carbon double bond conjugated to the carbonyl group, rarely have electrophilic double bonds [26]. Nevertheless, the β carbon from these compounds is the most electrophilic since it partially shares the positive carbon charge of the carbonyl group by resonance (see Figure 1.8).

Figure 1.8: Schematic depiction of Michael acceptor.

The Michael addition of a nucleophilic compound and α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds is a convenient route for constructing C-C and C-N bonds. This addition is also termed as 1,4 addition, which results from adding a nucleophile and a hydrogen atom to the conjugated carbon double bond. When the nucleophile attacks an α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds on β position, the oxygen atom is the fourth if it starts counting from nucleophile, and the addition produced is called 1,4 addition (Figure 1.9-a). Nevertheless, the nucleophile may attack the carbonyl group; when this occurs, oxygen protonation is produced, resulting in 1,2 addition, in which the nucleophile is added to an adjacent carbon atom and the hydrogen proton the oxygen atom (Figure 1.9-b).

Figure 1.9: a) 1,2 addition, step 1: nucleophile addition to C = O group, step 2: protonation. b) 1,4 addition (Michael addition), step 1: conjugate addition of nucleophile, step 2: protonation.

The way nucleophiles react either on the β position, or the carbonyl group depends on the reaction conditions, the nature of the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compound and the type of nucleophile [27], which are summarized in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Conjugate (1,4 or Michael) vs. direct (1,2) addition.

	Conjugate addition favored by	Direct addition to C=O favored by
Reaction conditions (for reversible additions):	Thermodynamic control: high temperatures, long reaction times	Kinetic control: low temperatures, short reaction times
Structure of α,β -unsaturated compound:	Unreactive carbonyl group (amide, ester)	Reactive carbonyl group (aldehyde, acyl chloride)
Type of nucleophile:	Soft nucleophiles (controlled by orbital overlap)	Hard nucleophiles (controlled by electrostatic forces)

The most frequent Michael donors are enolate ions, which are stabilized by two strong withdrawing groups, carbonyl, cyano, and nitro groups (those are the most common acceptors since having a conjugate double bond). These enolates are formed qualitatively from common bases. Without need extra bases that can attack the Michael acceptor. Table 1.2 are summarized the main compounds that may be used as Michael donors and Michael acceptors.

One interesting aspect of the reaction kinetics of Michael addition is the choice of base catalyst, which has a tremendous effect on it. The pK_a of the Michael, the donor is important to the choice of base catalyst, which must have a pK_a for its conjugated acid in the same range as the Michael donor. Stronger bases such as tetramethylguanidine, with a pK_a of 13.6 in its protonated form, are needed in the case of the carbon Michael addition of enolates due to the high pK_a of the acetoacetate groups ($pK_{a1} = 12$, $pK_{a2} = 13.6$). Base catalysts are often unnecessary in the case of amines because of the strong nucleophilicity of the nitrogen atom, whereas weak bases aid in the deprotonation of thiols.

It has been studied the ability of bases such as tetramethylguanidine, triethylamine, 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene, and 1,5-diazabicyclo[4.3.0]non-5-ene and found that the rate of the reaction was dependent on catalyst concentration [28]. For strong bases such as hydroxide, a steady-state concentration of enolate anion is achieved, and pseudo-first-order kinetics were observed.

Table 1.2: The most common donors and acceptors of Michael.

Michael donors		Michael acceptors	
	Conjugate aldehyde		
	Conjugate ketone		
R_2CuLi	Diakyl cuprate		Conjugate ester
	Conjugate amide		
	Conjugate nitrile		
	Nitro-ethylene		

1.3.1 The aza-Michael reaction

The variety of Michael reactions that uses nucleophilic nitrogen is known as the aza-Michael reaction. This addition is used widely for carbon-nitrogen bond formation in modern organic synthetic chemistry. Conjugation addition of various amines with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compound provides β -amino carbonyl components, which have attracted great attention for their use as key intermediates of anticancer agents, antibiotics and other drugs. [29]–[32].

Amines are organic compounds derived from ammoniac with alkyl or aryl groups bonded to a nitrogen atom. Amines are classified in primary, secondary and tertiary according to whether nitrogen atom is bonded with one, two or three alkyl or aryl groups. An amine is a nucleophile (Lewis base) due to lone pair of non-bonding electrons that can form a bond with an electrophile. It can also act as a Brønsted-Lowry base, accepting one proton from an acid. Figure 1.10.

Amines are strongly polar due to the large dipole moment of the electron lone pair joined to the dipole moments of C-N and H-N bonds. Primary and secondary amines possess N-H bonds, which form hydrogen bonds. Since they have no N-H bonds, Tertiary amines do not form hydrogen bonds; however, they can participate as hydrogen bond acceptors with molecules that have O-H or N-H bonds. Since amines can act as both nucleophiles and bases, typically, it is not necessary to add a base in the aza-Michael reaction.

Figure 1.10: a) Behaviour of the amine as a nucleophile, b) Behaviour of the amine as a base.

As mentioned, alkyl groups are electron donors. For example, if we consider the relative basicities of ammoniac and methylamine when then reacting with a water molecule, it can be observed in Figure 1.11 that methylamine has a methyl group, this help to ‘stabilize’ the nitrogen positive charge. This ‘stabilization’ decreases the potential energy of methylammonium cation, making methylamine a stronger base than ammoniac.

Figure 1.11: a) Reaction of ammoniac with a water molecule, b) Reaction of methylamine with a water molecule.

Hence, secondary amines are stronger bases (nucleophilic for aza-Michael reaction purpose) than primary amines, and tertiary amines are stronger bases of the three. However, it should be noted that this depends on the electronic and steric environment of the amine. For example, 1,4-butanediol diacrylate was allowed to react with 1-(2-aminoethyl)piperazine in an equimolar ratio Figure 1.12 [33]. During the initial part of the experience, it was found that reaction had occurred exclusively with the secondary amine present in the piperazine ring. After a certain reaction time, the reaction proceeded with the primary amine, which led to polymerization.

Figure 1.12: Higher reactivity of secondary amines in aza-Michael addition reactions.

Primary amines can react with two equivalents of acceptor to form tertiary amines. In some cases, this second addition affects the observed kinetics, especially as the concentration of the secondary amine increases. An example is the reaction of methyl amine with ethyl acrylate, giving an excellent yield of the tertiary amine (Figure 1.13) [34].

Figure 1.13: Aza-Michael addition of methyl amine to two equivalents of ethyl acrylate.

1.3.2 Other Michael donors

Thiols can be used as donors in the Michael addition; they are generally more nucleophilic than amines, although bases are often used to deprotonate them due to their comparatively higher acidity. The thiolate anion is often the active species in Michael additions with thiols. The thiol-Michael addition reaction rates increase with pH due to the increased concentration of the thiolate anion [35]. One primary side reaction in thiol-Michael addition is disulfide bond formation, which often prompts protecting group chemistry. Some reports have been presented describing the use of thiols as a Michael donor [36]. For instance, the enzyme catalysis of the thiol addition can be

nominated to 2-butenal [37]. The enzyme's active site in this reaction is exemplified in Figure 1.14. Unexpectedly, aqueous sodium dodecyl sulfate solutions perform as powerful catalysts of the Michael additions of thiols or amines to enones [38].

Figure 1.14: Thiol-Michael addition in wild *Candida Antarctica* lipase B [42].

Carbon-based nucleophiles are another class of donors used in Michael addition reactions. The best-known carbon-Michael reaction is the base-catalyzed addition of ethyl acetoacetate to methyl acrylate [25]. The acetoacetate is first deprotonated by the base, providing an enolate anion (Michael donor) in equilibrium (as seen in Figure 1.15). Then the enolate anion reacts in a 1,4-conjugate addition to the olefin of acrylate (Michael acceptor). The carbonyl group of the acrylate regenerates the base since it stabilizes the resulting anion until proton transfer occurs. The force that controls the addition is the enthalpic change that occurs when is replaced a π -bond with a σ -bond. Thereby, there is the preference for 1,4 addition over 1,2 addition. However, controlling the kinetics reaction can be attacked the carbonyl carbon instead of β -carbon of the olefin. In Figure 1.15, it can be observed that the rate-determining step is the attack of the enolate anion on the activated olefin. Therefore, the reaction rate is second-order and first-order concerning the enolate anion and the olefin acceptor.

Figure 1.15: General carbon-Michael reaction mechanistic scheme.

1.4 Hyperbranched polymers

As nitrogen-donor in the Michael addition, hyperbranched polymers containing amines may be used. They can modify the properties of the final thermosetting material due to the core structure, the degree of branching and the type of functional end-groups [39]. Investigations in which was employed HPBs based on amines (e.g., hyperbranched polyethyleneimine) have been reported; for example, in [40], it has been demonstrated that using a hyperbranched poly(ethyleneimine) as a curing agent of DGEBA, the curing mechanism is very similar when a low molecular weight aliphatic amine such as DETA (diethylenetriamine) is used. In both cases, a general epoxy-amine polycondensation mechanism is detected. However, the curing kinetics are slower using HPBs than DETA because of the lower mobility of HPBs. They observed that gelation takes place earlier with HPBs because the higher functionality of the hyperbranched amine decreases the conversion at the gel point. Another example is described in [41], where they observed that HPB polyethyleneimine and other similar modifiers are capable of accelerating the curing of DGEBA mixtures with MI (1-methylimidazole) as initiator due to the positive effect of hydroxyl groups formed by condensation on the anionic curing of epoxides with tertiary amines.

Hyperbranched polymers have attracted much attention due to their distinct structures and properties from their linear analogs and wide applications [42], [43]. These polymers present many advantages, such as structural versatility, due to their high ramification and the presence of many terminal reactive groups, and low viscosity concerning linear analogs.

These types of polymers are used to reduce the internal stresses of thermosets. These stresses appear due to thermoset contraction during curing process. One of their most relevant applications in thermosetting formulations is toughening agents controlled by phase separation during the curing process [44], [45]. For example, it has been noted that the shell chemical design of the HBPs can induce a 20% increase in K_{IC} for 5 wt% HBP modified resins [46]. In addition, they observe that in the HBP-toughened resin, one of the toughening mechanisms observed is particle cavitation. These particles induce large stress concentrations, which lead to extensive shear deformation, a high toughened-absorbing mechanism. The high toughening capacity of HBP modifiers result from the high interaction level generated by the large number of chemical bonds formed between the particles and each HBP molecule. HPBs polymers are also used as crosslinking agents or reactive additives both in thermal-induced curing [47] and photo-induced curing [48], [49]. For instance, it has been found that the epoxy group conversion increase by increasing the amount of HBP (specifically HBP-H20) in a photo curable mixture [50].

Up to now, the synthetic techniques used to prepare hyperbranched polymers could be divided into two categories [51]. The first category contains techniques of the single-monomer methodology (SMM), in which hyperbranched macromolecules are synthesized by polymerization of an AB_n or a latent AB_n monomer. According to the reaction mechanism, the category includes at least four specific approaches: polycondensation of AB_n monomers; self-condensing vinyl polymerization; self-condensing ring-opening polymerization; proton-transfer polymerization. The other category contains systems of the double-monomer methodology in which direct polymerization of two types of monomers or a monomer pair generates hyperbranched polymers.

The HBP term often is used to define dendritic macromolecules that have random branch-on-branch topology by single-step polycondensation of AB_2 -type monomers (with $f \geq 2$) [52]. Polycondensation of, e.g., AYB_2 with trifunctional branch point Y and reactive groups A and B in shown in Figure 1.16.

Figure 1.16: Scheme polycondensation of AYB_2 .

The reaction delivers branched molecules at all monomers conversions; the polymers never become cross-linked. The molecules has terminal groups B and are non-uniform with respect to composition and constitution and thus also to molar mass. They can be imagined as irregular comb polymers with subsequent branching of the side chains. The step-growth polycondensation route had been utilized extensively in the synthesis of a diverse range of hyperbranched systems as many functionalities are tolerated.

Continuing in the same single-monomer methodology, it appears the self-condensing vinyl polymerization, which is based on a vinyl monomer that additional bears an initiating group (“inimer” = initiator + monomer) [53]. These monomers allow propagation through the double bond (=chain growth) and addition of the initiating site to the double bond (=step growth). Thereby, they lead to hyperbranched polymers in a one-pot reaction with possible branching in each repeating unit and, thus, with the potential to reach a degree of branching of 50% depending on the reactivity ratio of the A^* or B^* end groups. The self-condensing ring-opening polymerization differs from self-condensing vinyl polymerization in the fact that instead of a vinyl group a heterocyclic group is used as the monomer part of the inimer. In addition, whereas in self-condensing vinyl polymerization usually irreversible reactions are involved, in self-condensing ring-opening polymerization also reversible preconditions generally have to be considered. The self-condensing ring-opening polymerization approaches have their origin in classical ring-opening reaction mechanism toward linear polymers. Commercial poly(ethyleneimine) prepared by self-condensing ring-opening reaction of aziridine is a branched polymer due to further reaction of the NH groups in the formed polymer chain with the cyclic monomer.

The other category, double-monomer methodology can be divided into two main subclasses based on the selected monomer pairs and different reaction pathways. The classical one, the polymerization of A_2 and B_3 (or B_n , $n > 2$) monomers can be called the ‘ $A_2 + B_3$ ’ methodology. As a consequence of the infrequent commercial availability of AB_2 monomers, studies have begun to focus towards the polycondensation of A_2 and B_3 monomers. The success of this approach is dependent upon many factors, including the ratio of functionalities, solvent and reagent purity and the reaction time and temperature [54]. This type of polymerization has proved difficult to control and hyperbranched polymers are often obtained with high molecular masses. There have been three main polymer architectures known to date, polyamides, polycarbonates and polyureas. Although the $A_2 + B_3$ approach to hyperbranched polymers holds some merit over the conventional AB_2 polycondensation approach, such as facile preparation and commercial availability of monomers, it still exhibit the major problem of uncontrollable gelation, especially under conditions of relatively high monomer concentration and high reaction temperature. To avoid cross-linking, the reaction must be performed under low monomer concentration or slow monomer addition, or the polymerization must be stopped prior to the critical point gelation. This limits the wide applications of $A_2 + B_3$ approach in large-scale manufacture of hyperbranched polymers. For that reason a new strategy called couple-monomer methodology was crated. This methodology presents commercial availability of monomer and lack of incidence of gelation.

At present, eight subclasses of dendritic polymers have been developed (Figure 1.17), of which the first four subclasses have the perfect and ideally branched structures with the degree of branching (DB) of 1.0 and the latter four exhibit a random and irregular branched configuration with lesser DB (normally, 0.4-0.6).

Figure 1.17: Dendritic polymers with different structures. (a) Dendrimer, (b) linear-dendritic hybrid, (c) dendronized polymer, (d) DendriMacro, (e) hyperbranched polymer, (f) multiarm star polymer or hyperbranched polymer brush, (g) HP-grafted polymer, and (h) HyperMacro.

For comparison, the characteristics and properties of HPs are summarized in Table 1.3 with both linear polymers and dendrimers [55]. Usually, HPs show ellipsoid-like 3D architecture, randomly branched structure with $DB < 1.0$, wide polydispersity of MW (normally, $PDI > 3.0$), little molecular entanglement, low viscosity, high solubility, and plenty of functional groups linked at both the linear and terminal units. Based on their cost-effective and large-scale productivity, HPs are preferred in industrial applications as compared with dendrimers.

Table 1.3: Comparison of Hyperbranched Polymer with linear Polymer and Dendrimer.

Polymer	Linear	Hyperbranched	Dendrimer
Structure			
Topology	1D, Linear	3D, ellipsoidal	3D, globular
Synthesis	One-step, facile	One-step, cost effective	Multistep, laborious
MW	Mixed MWs	Mixed MWs	Same MWs
PDI	>1.1	>3.0	1.0(<1.05)
DB	0	0.4-0.6	1.0
Molecular cavity	No	Reversible box	Irreversible box
Entanglement	Strong	Weak	Very weak or no

Environmentally-friendly processing of thermosets by two-stage sequential aza-Michael addition and free-radical polymerization of amine-acrylate mixtures

Viscosity	High	Low	Very low
Solubility	Low	High	Very high
Functional groups	At two ends	At linear and terminal units	At terminal units
Reactivity	Low	High	Very high
Strength	High	Low	Very low

2. Materials, techniques and methodology

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Acrylates

1,6-Hexanediol diacrylate (HDDA, $M_w = 226,27$ g/mol), Bisphenol A glycerolate (1 glycerol/phenol) diacrylate (BGDA, $M_w = 484,54$ g/mol) and Trimethylolpropane Triacrylate (TMPTA, $M_w = 296,32$ g/mol) monomers supplied by Aldrich were used to provide acrylate reactive monomers for sample preparation.

The HDDA is used as a functional monomer for polymers and as a crosslinking agent between the molecular chains of polymers. This substance also known as acrylic acid, undergoes the typical reactions of a carboxylic acid and forms acrylic esters-basic alkyl esters are methyl, butyl, ethyl acrylate, and 2-ethylhexyl acrylate. Acrylic acid and its esters undergo the reactions of the double bond which readily combine with themselves or other monomers (e.g. amides, methacrylates, acrylonitrile, vinyl, styrene and butadiene) to form homopolymers or co-polymers which are used in the production of coatings, adhesives, elastomers, super absorbent polymers, flocculants, as well as fibers and plastics.

Whereas, the BGDA is a difunctional acrylate that could be used as a UV curable cross-linking agent, coatings, component of curable inks, varnishes and lacquers. Among its main characteristics and advantages, may be mentioned high viscosity and non-volatile substance. Likewise, the trifunctional monomer TMTA may be used in the production of UV curable inks, electron beam irradiation-curable coatings, polymers and resins; as a component of photopolymer and flexographic printing plates and photoresists, as an ingredient in acrylic glues and anaerobic sealants. In addition, it is used in paper and wood impregnates, wire and cable extrusion, polymer-impregnated concrete and polymer concrete structural composites. The chemical structures of the monomers used to provide acrylate groups are shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Chemical structure HDDA, BGDA and TMTA.

2.1.2 Methacrylates

As methacrylate reactive monomers were used Triethylene glycol-dimethacrylate (TEGDMA, $M_w = 286.3$ g/mol), this compound was supplied by Aldrich and used as received. The TEGDMA is a hydrophilic difunctional methacrylate monomer that can be employed as a crosslinking agent or low viscosity reactive diluent in a variety of applications such as: anaerobic adhesives, sealants, UV-cured coatings, photopolymers for solder masks and circuit boards, and fuel-resistant metal parts. This substance is also typically used in dental resin materials that can cause specific stress responses in eukaryotic cells. The chemical structures both TEGDMA used for the sample preparation are seen in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Chemical structure of TEGDMA.

2.1.3 Amines

To take place the aza-Michael addition, three different reagents containing amine were used: Jeffamine D-2320 Polyetheramine (JEFF, $M_w = 230$ g/mol), Poly(ethyleneimine) Lupasol FG (LPFG, $M_w = 800$ g/mol) and Diethylenetriamine (DETA, $M_w = 103,17$ g/mol). All amines were used as received. The ratio of primary/secondary/tertiary amine group in LPFG, DETA and JEFF is 1.0/0.82/0.53, 1.0/0.5/0.0 and 1.0/0.0/0.0 respectively and their degree of branching 0.56, 0 [41] and 0 respectively.

The Jeffamine is a difunctional primary amine supplied by Huntsman Company. It is characterized by repeating oxypropylene units in the backbone. The primary amine groups are located on secondary carbon atoms at the end of the aliphatic polyether chain. It presents a low viscosity, is completely miscible with a wide variety of solvents, including water, and provides tough, impact resistant coating, castings and adhesives.

Another amine used was the Lupasol FG; this supplied by BASF Company is a multifunctional cationic polyethylenimine with a branched polymeric structure. Due to their high charge density, they adsorb tightly on negatively charged surfaces. This modus operandi can be applied to a huge variety of materials, such as cellulose, polyesters, polyolefines, polyamides, and metals, and provides visible advantages to the user. Its main characteristics and properties are, low molecular weight highly charges, cationic ethylenimine copolymer, clear to slightly turbid, colorless to pale yellow and viscous liquid. Polyethylenimine Lupasol® FG is an excellent cross-linker for other polymers. It promotes adhesion of wood laminates, cement and bricks. It enhances the effectiveness of wood preservatives, adheres to metal surfaces and improves corrosion inhibitors.

The last amine employed was the DETA, it was provided by Sigma Aldrich and it is commonly used in the manufacture of paper wet-strength resins, corrosion inhibitors, fuel additives, epoxy curing agents, fabric softeners and asphalt additives among other applications. It is the second linear member of the ethyleneamines family and contains two primary and one secondary amine groups. It is clear and colorless with an ammonia-like odor; DETA is a single component product.

The chemical structure of amines involved in the aza-Michael reaction for this project is seen in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Chemical structure of TEGDMA and BGDMA

2.1.4 Catalytic systems (Initiators)

Dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone (DMPA) was used as photoinitiator type I; it can be applied in the present dual curing model to activate homopolymerization of acrylate/methacrylate groups in excess by UV radiation after the aza-Michael stage. In addition, Benzophenone (BENP) was used as photoinitiator type II to activate homopolymerization of acrylate/methacrylate monomers in excess by UV light in the current dual-curing model. Figure 2.4 show the molecular structure of DMPA and BENP.

Figure 2.4: Molecular Structure scheme of DMPA and BENP.

Methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) and benzoyl peroxide in water with a content of 70% mass (BPOX) were used as thermal initiator. They are widely used in the polymer industry for curing unsaturated resins, are strong oxidizing agents, may be ignited by heat, sparks or flame, and undergoes self-accelerating decomposition and it is sensitive to sunlight. They can react with combustible materials such as wood, cloth or organic materials, with chlorine, and with metals (iron, copper and their alloys and aluminium and its alloys) and are incompatible with strong oxidizing agents, strong reducing agents, natural rubbers, synthetic rubbers and chemical accelerators. In addition, they are incompatible with heavy metals, acids and bases. Cobalt (II) octoate 0.5% solution in phthalate (OCO) supplied by AkzoNobel was used as promoter. This substance is used as a drier for coatings, as well as an initiator and cross-linker for polyester manufacturing. Cobalt octoate accelerates the catalytic action of Methyl ethyl ketone (MEKP) peroxide to polymerize unsaturated polyester resin. Figure 2.5 shows the chemical structure of MEKP, BPOX and OCO.

Figure 2.5: Molecular structure of MEKP, BPOX and OCO.

2.2 Preparation of formulations

For the realization of this thesis, were prepared formulations containing mixtures of amines and acrylates with different ratios between them. The procedure to obtain these samples is described as follows: first, the initiator is added in a vial with the diacrylates mixture and stirred mechanically until the mixture became clear at room temperature. Then the amine was added to the abovementioned mixture, stirred mechanically and degassed under vacuum at 35°C for 15 minutes. For the aza-Michael reaction, the stoichiometric ratio between acrylate groups and reactive amine hydrogens may be define as r . The acrylate group conversion can be defined as α , consequently, the conversion of amine groups is calculated as $r \cdot \alpha$. In the case of $r > 1$, the expected maximum conversion of acrylate groups in the aza-Michael will be equal to $1/r$, and therefore the remaining acrylate groups can further polymerize when the radical initiator present in the system is activated with UV-light or temperature.

Formulations containing different ratios between reactive amine hydrogens and double bonds are then coded as $1:r$. The notation used in this project also reflects the composition in wt.% of the acrylates. As an example, LPFG/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:8 formulation, contains 25 g. of BGDA per 75 g. of HDDA and 1 N-H bond coming from LPFG per 8 acrylate groups. Formulations 1:8, 1:4, 1:2 and 1:1 (corresponding to a maximum of 12.5, 25, 50 and 100% conversion of double bonds in the aza-Michael reaction with respect to the total curing process) and a 3 wt.% of photoinitiator with respect to the diacrylates mixture were prepared.

For comparison purposes, were also prepared neat acrylate formulations without amine. Mixtures of acrylates containing a 3 wt.% of DMPA as photoinitiator were used as reference materials, but for comparison purposes methacrylates, a type II photoinitiator and a thermal free-radical initiator were also been studied. In these cases, the formulations were prepared in a similar manner to that previously reported for acrylate mixtures and the notation was also similar.

2.3 Experimental techniques

2.3.1 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out with a Mettler TGA/DSC 851e/LF/110 thermobalance, shown in Figure 2.6. Thermogravimetry measures the weight changes that occur when a sample is heated, cooled or held at constant temperature in a defined gas atmosphere using

a controlled temperature program. This technique is widely used for studying polymer degradation. The decomposition temperature gives an idea of thermal resistance of the sample, which may be related to its internal structure. Thermobalance operation is relatively simple since only has a precision balance inside a furnace and all is connected to a computer which experiences are scheduled.

Figure 2.6: Mettler TGA/SDTA 851e/LF/110 thermobalance.

In this project, thermogravimetric analysis was used to study the thermal stability of the dual cured final samples. The tests were performed under nitrogen atmosphere ($50 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$ measured in normal conditions) at a constant heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Samples with an approximate mass of 10 mg were introduced in silicon oxide crucibles as shown in Figure 2.7 and degraded between $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 2.7: Detail of the sample for Thermogravimetric analysis.

2.3.2 *Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)*

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is a technique that detects thermal phenomena such as phase changes or chemical reaction. The calorimeter used for analyses is the Mettler DSC-822e calorimeter with a TSO801RO robotic arm (shown in Figure 2.8) refrigerated through nitrogen liquid. The calorimeter was calibrated using an indium standard (heat flow calibration) and an indium-zinc standard (temperature calibration).

Figure 2.8: Mettler DSC-822e calorimeter with a TSO801RO robotic arm.

Samples with an approximate mass of 10 mg were placed in aluminium pans with capacity of approximately 40 μL as shown in Figure 2.9. , then, they were isothermally cured in oven for three hours at 35°C (aza-Michael addition, first stage of dual curing). The capsule cap is drilled a hole to release any possible volatile).

Figure 2.9: Detail of the sample for DSC analysis, a) sample positioning and b) aluminium cap closing by applying pressure.

The glass transition temperatures ($T_{g,s}$) of the obtained materials after the first curing step and of the amines and acrylate mixtures before curing (T_{g0}) were determined by means of a scan at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ from -125 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under nitrogen atmosphere, as the temperature of the half-way point of the jump in the heat capacity when the material changed from glassy to the rubbery state under N_2 atmosphere. The error is estimated to be approximately $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2.3.3 Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR/ATR)

A Bruker Vertex 70 FTIR spectrometer equipped with an attenuated total reflection (ATR) device (seen in Figure 2.10.) which is temperature controlled (heated single-reflection diamond ATR crystal) was used to monitor the degree of conversion of acrylate groups during isothermal dual curing at 35°C of the formulations.

Figure 2.10: Vertex 70 spectrometer Brukers and detail of ATR device

Real-time spectra were collected at 35°C in absorbance mode with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and a wavelength range from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹, averaging 20 scans for each spectrum. A Hamamatsu Lightningcure LC5 (Hg-Xe lamp) with one beam conveniently adapted to ATR accessory was used to irradiate the samples during the second curing stage. Samples for studying of isothermal degree conversion do not need previous preparation and they can be directly deposited (around 25 μm of thickness) on diamond head of the ATR device by a wire-wound rod. The dual curing process was performed in a similar way to the samples described above, three hours without irradiation (first stage) followed for 1 minute of UV-irradiation (second stage). It was observed that final acrylate/methacrylate conversion was barely modified using higher irradiation times. Spectra were registered during first stage and at the end of the second stage. Neat formulations without amine were cured in an inert atmosphere.

To obtain information from FTIR spectra about the progress of the reaction against time, firstly, it is necessary to normalize all spectra using a reference signal of some specie that remain unchanged during curing process. Thereby, it has been used as reference band the signal corresponding to carbonyl ester band at 1720 cm⁻¹[56],[57]. Thereafter, some characteristic peaks appear in the normalized FTIR spectra corresponding to different functional groups present in the formulations, seen in Figure 2.11. The curing profile was monitored by following the evolution of peaks at 809 cm⁻¹ and 1407 cm⁻¹ corresponding to carbon-carbon double bond of vinyl compound from acrylate and/or methacrylate groups, which are reduced significantly after curing process[58]. The acrylate conversion was determined from the normalized change of absorbance at 1408 cm⁻¹ (band of the CH₂ scissor deformation mode) and the methacrylate conversion was calculated taking into account the acrylate/methacrylate composition in the formulation, the overall methacrylate/acrylate conversion given by the change of absorbance at 809 cm⁻¹ (C=C deformation) and the acrylate conversion.

Figure 2.11: Spectrum of one of the formulation obtained by FTIR.

According to Beer law (Equation 2.2), the absorbance of specie in a specific frequency is proportional to its molar absorptivity ε , to its concentration C and the optical path l of the absorption medium [59]. Therefore, absorbance quantitative study of different signals allows evaluate diverse species concentration or reactive groups and in particular, monitoring curing processes.

$$A = \varepsilon \cdot C \cdot l \quad (2.1)$$

It can be defined a normalized absorbance of a specific functional group. As acrylate, methacrylate group or both, in a reaction time t as $\bar{A} = A_{fg,t}/A_{ref,t}$ and an initial normalized absorbance as $\bar{A}_0 = A_{fg,0}/A_{ref,0}$. Therefore, the reaction conversion $\alpha(t)$ may be calculated from the functional group disappearance as (Equation 2.2):

$$\alpha(t) = 1 - \frac{\bar{A}_t}{\bar{A}_0} \quad (2.2)$$

Where $A_{fg,t}$ and $A_{fg,0}$ are the absorbance of the functional groups at time t and at the start of the reaction respectively, $A_{ref,t}$ and $A_{ref,0}$ are the reference absorbance (pertaining to reference band at 1720 cm-1) at time t and at the start of the process respectively.

The progress of aza-Michael addition (first stage) was calculated according to the acrylate conversion and the N-H/acrylate ratio, taking account that each acrylate group react with one N-H group during this reaction. The reaction progress during the first reaction stage, named as aza-Michael reaction (%), was expressed as the ratio (%) between the N-H bonds reacted during the first stage and the N-H bond content of the formulation.

2.3.4 Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMAs) were carried out with a TA instruments DMA Q800 cooled by liquid nitrogen. DMA can be described as applying an oscillating force (at a certain frequency) to a sample and analysing the response of material to that force [60]. The oscillatory force causes a sinusoidal stress to be applied to the sample, which generates a sinusoidal strain. By measuring both the amplitude of the deformation at the peak of the sine wave and the lag between the stress and strain sine waves (known as δ), can be calculated quantities like the modulus, the viscosity, and the damping. Limit values of δ are 0° (purely elastic behavior) and 90° (purely viscous behavior). In DMA, an elastic modulus E' , and an imaginary (loss) modulus E'' are calculated from the material response to the sine wave. These different modules allow a better characterization of the material; Table 2.1 shows briefly the most important parameters that can be determined by DMA.

Table 2.1: Description of the parameters determined with DMA.

Parameter	Description
E'	Storage modulus. Represents the energy that the material stores due to the deformation, reversible and recoverable way.
E''	Losses modulus. Represents the energy dissipated by the material irreversibly.
$\tan \delta = (E''/E')$	Lag between tension and deformation waves. Relationship between amount of energy lost and recoverable energy in a deformation process. Represents The dissipation of energy in a material under cyclic.

One of most common uses of the DMA is the measurement of the various transitions in polymers, due to the greater sensitivity of the DMA respect to the differential scanning calorimeter (DSC). The DMA analyser can accurately detect structural relaxations of polymer materials such as the glass transition (also called relaxation α), which appears as a maximum on the curve of $\tan \delta$ as seen in Figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12: Curve of $\tan \delta$ vs temperature where it can be observed the glass transition (T_g).

In this project, rectangular samples were analysed using a low-friction three point bending clamp, at frequency of 1 Hz and deformation of 0,05%, with a $3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ from -150 to 250°C . The glass transition temperatures were assigned to the peak temperature of the $\tan \delta$ curve. The storage moduli in the rubbery state, E'_r , were determined at $\tan \delta$ peak + 50°C . This parameter is roughly

proportional to the crosslinking density, as deviations from the ideal rubber elasticity model are frequent in densely crosslinked thermosetting systems.

Fully cured samples for dynamic mechanical analysis were prepared in a glass or polypropylene mould (as shown in Figure 2.13) by isothermal dual curing in an oven at 35°C for 3 hours (aza-Michael addition) followed by UV-induced curing process at ambient temperature (photopolymerization of the unreacted acrylate/methacrylate groups). Each side of the sample was irradiated during UV-curing for 15 min with a monochromatic UV lamp of 365 nm wavelength and 4 mW/cm² of intensity. Prismatic rectangular samples (1 x 13 x 20 mm³) were prepared using this procedure. Longer curing times were tested in both stages, but the curing process did not advance substantially. The samples prepared were characterized at the end of both curing stages.

Figure 2.13: Details of sample preparation for analysis of DMTA a) b) c) and d).

2.3.5 Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA)

A thermo-mechanical analyser Mettler thermomechanical analysis SDTA840 was used to determine the gelation point during aza-Michael addition in samples (first stage). In this project, the sample was placed at 35°C during 3 h and subjected to an oscillatory force from 0.005 to 0.01 N with an oscillation frequency of 0.083 Hz. The gelation point was calculated as the time when the oscillation in the thickness of the sample is damped (as shown in Figure 2.14). The conversion to gelation was obtained as the conversion achieved in FTIR experiences at the temperature where the material turns into gel in the TMA.

Figure 2.14: TMA curve length vs time that shows the gelation point.

Specimens for this test were obtained when a thin glass fibre disc of 5 mm in diameter is impregnated with the liquid formulation and sandwiched between two small aluminium discs, shown in Figure 2.15.

Figure 2.15: Details of samples preparations for the thermomechanical analysis

Assuming no substitution effects are present (i.e. no different primary and secondary amine reactivity or size/structure dependent reactivity), conversion of acrylate groups at gelation during aza-Michael reaction of a hyperbranched amine and a bifunctional acrylate can be determined from the Stockmayer relationship.

$$\alpha_{gel} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{r \cdot (f_w - 1)}} \quad (2.3)$$

Where f_w is the amine functionality. Following Dušek and Duškova-Smrčková [61], this expression can also be used for hyperbranched crosslinking agents, but taking into account that f_w is the second moment or mass-averaged functionality of the hyperbranched crosslinker, defined in the case of a hyperbranched poly(ethyleneimine) as:

$$f_w = \frac{M_w}{M_a} \quad (2.4)$$

In the above expression, M_w is the mass-average molecular weight of the hyperbranched polymer (equal to 800 g/mol for Lupasol FG) and M_a is the mass of the ethyleneimine repeating unit (equal to 43 g/mol in the case of a hyperbranched polyethyleneimine). In spite of the presence of core ethylenediamine fragments in the polymer structure of Lupasol FG, there are a number of reasons supporting this expression of f_w :

- (1) Each polymerized aziridine monomer contributes, on average, to one reactive group in the HBP.
- (2) In the calculation of the second moment (or mass-average) more weight is given to polymer molecules with higher molecular mass and therefore higher amount of polymerized aziridine, therefore minimizing the effect of the presence of core molecules in the structure.
- (3) The structure of the ethylenediamine core is, in any case, very similar to that of the polymerized aziridine repeating units.

This expression is analogous to the well-known expression of Miller and Macosko [62], [1] for the mixture of monomers with different functionalities. Equation (2.4) has been used to determine the theoretical conversion of acrylate groups at the gel point, α_{gel} , for bifunctional acrylate formulations, using a f_w of 18.6 ($M_w/M_a=800/43$) for Lupasol FG, a f of 5 for diethylenetriamine (each DETA molecule has 5 N-H bonds that can react via aza-Michael reaction with an acrylate group), and a f of 4 for Jeffamine D-230.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of the amine

Amine-acrylate polymers based on a diacrylate mixture (25% wt. BGDA and 75% wt. HDDA) and a multifunctional amine (LPFG or DETA) or difunctional amine (JEFF) were selected to exhibit the potential value of the dual cure aza-Michael reaction/free radical polymerization to prepare tailor-made materials. These materials are storable and processable after the first curing step, and with a broad range of properties after completion of the second curing process. LPFG, DETA and JEFF were selected to stand out the effect of the degree of branching of the amine and the ratio of primary/secondary/tertiary amine groups on the dual curing and properties of the prepared materials.

In order to visualize the response of acrylate monomers in the presence of amines and the subsequent homopolymerization of the excess of them under UV irradiation, Figure 3.1 shows the FTIR spectrum against curing time of one of the formulations, specifically, DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:2 formulation with a 3 wt% of DMPA as photoinitiator. This mixture was selected since its spectrum shows clearly the acrylate groups evolution. It can be observed qualitatively the decreasing of acrylate groups concentration while the Michael reaction (first curing step) proceeds at 35 °C and the *quasi* complete disappearance of these when UV irradiation (second curing step) is applied for a minute. Another significant feature is that the Michael addition slows its reaction velocity as reaches to 180 minutes of curing time.

Figure 3.1: FTIR spectrum against curing time for DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:2 formulation with 3 wt.% of DMPA as photoinitiator, that shows the acrylate curing conversion at the 1408 cm⁻¹ band.

Table 3.1 and Table 3.2 expose the percent conversion of the acrylate groups after both curing stages for formulations containing LPFG, DETA and JEFF and a 3 wt. % of DMPA as photoinitiator and the most significant thermal-mechanical properties before and after each curing step for the same formulations.

Table 3.1: Acrylate conversion (%) and aza-Michael reaction (%) reached and some properties obtained before and after stage 1. The formulations contain a 25 wt. % of BGDA and 75 wt. % of HDDA, different ratios of LPFG, DETA or JEFF to acrylate functional groups and 3wt.% of DMPA as a photoinitiator.

Formulations	N-H / acrylate ratio	W _{amine} / W _{acrylate} (%)	T _{g0} (°C)	Stage 1		
				Acrylate conversion (%)	Aza-Michael reaction (%)	T _g (°C)
BGDA25/HDDA75 (Neat)			-94.0	0	0	-94.0
LPFG/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	3.2	-93.1	10	80	-92.4
	1:4	6.5	-92.2	19	76	-60.5
	1:2	12.9	-90.7	33	66	-59.6
	1:1	25.8	-87.9	62	62	-32.6
DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	2.0	-94.0	12	96	-92.6
	1:4	4.0	-94.0	23	92	-85.6
	1:2	8.0	-94.1	45	90	-66.5
	1:1	16.0	-94.1	73	73	-44.7
JEFF/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	5.7	-93.6	7	56	-92.1
	1:4	11.5	-93.2	13	52	-83.9
	1:2	23.0	-92.5	25	50	-71.5
	1:1	46.0	-91.5	47	47	-61.3

For the same formulations, the evolution of acrylate conversion corresponding to the aza-Michael reaction during the first curing stage, determined by in-situ FTIR/ATR monitoring is shown in Figure 3.2. Some characteristic trends can be observed:

- (1) Most of the reaction process takes place during the first 30 minutes.
- (2) After 180 minutes all the reaction reach a plateau.
- (3) When compare formulations containing DETA, LPFG and JEFF, those with DETA react faster and reach a higher degree of conversion than those containing LPFG, and the latter react faster, and reach a higher degree of conversion than those with JEFF.
- (4) Formulations with lower amine content react to a relative higher extent so that the aza-Michael reaction is closer to completion (see Table 3.1).

Table 3.2: Acrylate conversion and some properties obtained after stage 2. The formulations contain a 25 wt. % of BGDA and 75 wt. % of HDDA, different ratios of LPFG, DETA or JEFF to acrylate functional groups and 3wt.% of DMPA as a photoinitiator.

Formulations	N-H / acrylate ratio	W _{amine} / W _{acrylate} (%)	Stage2		
			Acrylate conversion (%)	T _{g∞} (°C)	E' r (MPa)
BGDA25/HDDA75 (Neat)			90	102	164
LPFG/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	3.2	91	72	100
	1:4	6.5	92	64	87
	1:2	12.9	97	53	65
	1:1	25.8	99	35	44
DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	2.0	99	74	92
	1:4	4.0	99	56	73
	1:2	8.0	93	39	44
	1:1	16.0	99	16	33
JEFF/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	5.7	92	67	86
	1:4	11.5	94	48	58
	1:2	23.0	94	10	26
	1:1	46.0	97	-4	15

The evolution of conversion during aza-Michael addition suggests that this reaction is controlled chemically in the early stages, up 30 minutes, but diffusion controlled at higher reaction times. The inspection of reaction medium showed a significant increase in viscosity above 30 minutes of curing, which slow down the diffusion. Vitrification of the material must be ruled since the temperature of reaction is above the T_g of the growing chains. After three hours of reaction the samples were stored at room temperature for six months, and it was observed that the T_g of the materials barely changed during storage.

This result suggests that the aza-Michael reaction may not proceed further (if incomplete), the materials are stable at long times and that they can be stored safely before the activation of the second curing stage by UV-irradiation.

Figure 3.2: Acrylate conversion (from FTIR/ATR experiments) during aza-Michael addition (first curing stage) against time obtained by the isothermal reaction at 35 °C of BGDA25/HDDA75 formulations with a 3 wt% of DMPA as a photoinitiator and different molar ratios of LPFG, DETA and JEFF, indicated in the legend. a) Molar ratio of 1:1 and 1:2 of acrylate groups. b) Molar ratio of 1:4 and 1:8 of acrylate groups. Horizontal dashes lines indicate the maximum acrylate conversion if aza-Michael addition would be completed for 1:8, 1:4 and 1:2 formulations.

Although aza-Michael reaction generally has a high efficiency, in some amine-rich formulations, especially when LPFG and JEFF is used, the conversion is not complete (see Table 3.1). Many authors have attributed a similar behaviour, to the different reactivity of primary and secondary amines, to the steric hindrance of polymer backbone that reduces the reactivity of the secondary amines formed and to the diffusivity of growing chain in the reaction medium [33] [63] [64]. Moreover, it can be taken into account that the Michael reaction takes place through two equilibrium steps thermodynamically controlled by the strengths of the base and type of

nucleophile (in our case the amine can act as both nucleophile and base) [25]. *Wu et al.* [33] investigated the effects of chemistry of trifunctional amines on mechanisms of aza-Michael addition polymerizations with diacrylates. They established that the reactivity sequence of the three types of amine was secondary amines (original) > primary amines > secondary amines (formed), but reactivity sequence changed to primary amines > secondary amines (original) > secondary amines (formed) when the steric hindrance of secondary amines (original) was increased. These authors also observed that secondary amines, formed during aza-Michael addition, were unable to participate in the polymerization process, and kept unreacted.

According to these results, it can be rationalized that the differences observed in the reactivity of formulations containing DETA, LPFG and JEFF, can be related to the different types of amines (primary and secondary) content and to the accessibility of N-H bonds. Of all the potentially reactive amine hydrogens, LPFG contains 29 % of original secondary amines, 35.5 % that may react as primary and 35.5 % of formed secondary amines. DETA contains only a 20 % of original secondary amines, 40 % that may react as primary amines and 40 % of formed secondary amines, and JEFF contains 100 % of primary amines. In the case of DETA, the contribution of original secondary amines and primary amines (reacting as such) is 60 %, and this ratio coincides well with the change of slope in the conversion curves, taking into account the reagents ratio. Although this contribution is somewhat higher for LPFG, the topological restrictions imposed by the densely branched structure of LPFG, with a significant amount of tertiary amine groups, reduce the reactivity of the original secondary amines and possibly further more of the formed amines, resulting in a higher number of unreacted secondary amines, original or formed. For the case of JEFF formulations, 100 % of primary amine groups are involved in the aza-Michael addition; however, the secondary amines formed remained unreacted due to structural topological obstacles. Furthermore, the presence of primary amines still unreacted, disfavours the reactivity of secondary amines just formed. Amine-poor formulations reach a quasi-complete aza-Michael reaction for DETA amines, due the lower topological restrictions and the overall higher mobility of the reactive species. It has to be considered that only a small part of the reagents are involved in the aza-Michael reaction and the molecular weight of the growing polymer is significantly lower in amine-poor formulations.

During the second curing stage, the acrylate conversion increases significantly due to the free-radical homopolymerization of the excess of acrylate monomers (see Table 3.2). All formulations reach acrylate conversion between 90 and 100%, similar or even higher than that reached by the neat formulation without amine. As seen in Table 3.1, there is a significant increase in T_g after the first curing stage, especially in the amine-rich formulations, but the results suggest that the intermediate network structure (if present) does not interfere with or even favours crosslinking during the second curing stage. It can be concluded that the proposed dual curing methodology in general leads to nearly completely cured materials.

The gelation during aza-Michael reaction was studied by isothermal FTIR/TMA combined experiments at 35°C, these results are summarized in Table 3.3. The conversion at the gelation point, α_{gel} , is strongly affected by stoichiometric ratio and by the kind of amine, as predicted by equation (2.3). Formulations containing LPFG reach gelation at lower conversion than those containing DETA according to the higher functionality of LPFG ($f_w=18.6$) in comparison with DETA ($f=5$). As predicted by equation (2.3), DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:8 formulation and all formulations containing JEFF (due to its low functionality of $f=4$) did not gel during aza-Michael reaction. Table 3.3 shows that the theoretical conversion at gelation, $\alpha_{gel}^{theoretical}$, and the experimental ones, $\alpha_{gel}^{experimental}$, follow the same trend for LPFG and DETA: increasing with the

amine content. However, the experimental values are always slightly higher. In Table 3.3, it can also be observed that t_{gel} increases significantly on decreasing the amine content, due to the decrease in the reaction rate caused by the lower concentration of amine groups. Following the above line of reasoning for the analysis of the conversion curves, the differences between experimental and theoretical values can be explained by:

- (1) The significantly lower reactivity of formed secondary amine groups
- (2) The densely branched structure of LPFG leading to topological restrictions that also reduce the reactivity of original secondary amines.

Table 3.3: Experimental gelation data (α_{gel} and t_{gel}) obtained by isothermal FTIR/TMA combined experiments at 35°C. Theoretical α_{gel} obtained by using equation (2). The formulations contain a 25% wt. of BGDA and 75% wt. of HDDA and different ratios of LP or DETA to acrylate functional groups.

Formulation	N-H / acrylate ratio	W _{amine} / W _{acrylate} (%)	$\alpha_{gel}^{experimental}$	$\alpha_{gel}^{theoretical}$	t_{gel} (min)
LPFG/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	3.2	0.12	0.08	445.2
	1:4	6.5	0.16	0.12	48.5
	1:2	12.9	0.20	0.17	28.2
	1:1	25.8	0.26	0.23	17.5
DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	2.0	Not gelled		
	1:4	4.0	0.25	0.25	127.4
	1:2	8.0	0.40	0.35	95.8
	1:1	16.0	0.62	0.50	4.6
JEFF/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	5.7	Not gelled		
	1:4	11.5	Not gelled		
	1:2	23.0	Not gelled		
	1:1	46.0	Not gelled		

Both factors tend to increase the conversion at gelation that can be expected for an ideal system [1]. It has to take into account also the experimental error arising due to the combination of data from different techniques and accurate evaluation of acrylate conversion from FTIR data. Nevertheless, the similarity between theoretical and experimental data makes it possible to anticipate which formulations gelify during aza-Michael addition and estimate the conversion achieved at the gel point with a fair degree of accuracy.

Table 3.2 shows some relevant thermo-mechanical properties of the networked poly(amino ester)-poly(acrylate)s obtained at the final of dual curing process. Formulations containing LPFG, DETA and JEFF present a significant increase on T_g during the second stage of curing, depending on the extent of acrylate conversion during this stage. Even in 1:1 formulations, the presence of

unreacted acrylate groups after the aza-Michael reaction leads to a significant increase in crosslinking. In Table 3.2, it can also be seen that rubbery moduli increase proportionally to the homopolymerization of acrylate groups in the second curing stage. This can be expected from the densely crosslinked structure of amine-free BGDA25/HDDA75 formulation. It should be taken into account that diacrylates have a functionality of 2 in aza-Michael addition, but their functionality is 4 in diacrylate homopolymerization, as sketched in Figure 3.3. In consequence, formulations with higher proportion of acrylates lead to thermosets with higher crosslinking density, while formulations with higher amine content should lead to more loosely crosslinked materials with lower T_g . The comparison between both sets of systems shows that LPFG formulations have higher T_g and crosslinking density than DETA and JEFF formulations, due to the densely branched structure of LPFG, leading to the activation of internal branching points and further network mobility restrictions [65],[41].

Figure 3.3: Scheme methodology for dual-network formation from amine-acrylate mixtures.

Figures 3.4 and 3.5 plot the evolution of $\tan \delta$ and storage modulus (E') of LPFG and DETA final materials, respectively. Since in JEFF formulations remain secondary amines unreacted and do not gel after the aza-Michael addition, they are not taken into account for DMA analysis. In agreement with the data shown in Table 3.1, in formulations with higher amine content and therefore higher contribution of the aza-Michael reaction the network relaxation curves are shifted towards lower temperatures, indicating a decrease in T_g . This effect are more remarkable in DETA due to their lower functionality and the absence of internal branching points, in comparison with LPFG. It can also be observed that the α -relaxations (related to the T_g) of all materials are unimodal, indicating that all thermosets have homogeneous network structures, but acrylate-rich formulations show a more disperse network, as seen from the larger $\tan \delta$ peak and modulus drop step. Figures 3.4 and 3.5 besides show that the glassy storage modulus is higher in amine rich formulations in spite of their lower degree of crosslinking. This result can be justified in terms of cohesive energy density (CED), higher for DETA and LPFG than for diacrylate mixture. The CED values calculated using the group contributions according to the method outlined by Van Krevelen [66] were 863 MPa for DETA and LPFG and 703 MPa for BGDA25/HDDA75.

Figure 3.4: Storage moduli and $\tan \delta$ curves against temperature of dual cured BGDA/HDDA75 formulations with a 3 wt% of DMPA as a photoinitiator and different molar ratios of LPFG/acrylate, indicated in the legend.

Figure 3.5: Storage moduli and $\tan \delta$ curves against temperature of dual cured BGDA/HDDA75 formulations with a 3 wt% of DMPA as a photoinitiator and different molar ratios of DETA/acrylate, indicated in the legend.

Figure 3.6 shows the thermogravimetric curve for neat and DETA formulations. It can be noted in Figure 3.6.a and Figure 3.6.b that the degradation takes place in two steps. The first one at low temperature range can be related with the degradation of the poly(amino ester) structure due to the high content of labile C-N bonds. The degradation step at higher temperature, by comparison with the degradation of neat material, can be clearly assigned to the degradation of the poly(acrylate) structure. The mass loss associated to each step (shown in Figure 3.6) agrees approximately with the amino and acrylate content of the formulation.

Figure 3.6: a) Thermogravimetric and b) degradation rate curves at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ under a nitrogen atmosphere of dual cured BGDA25/HDDA75 formulations with a 3 wt% of DMPA as a photoinitiator and different molar ratios of DETA/acrylate, indicated in the legend.

This result suggests that the amine and the diacrylates degrade quasi separately during the first and second step respectively, but this in turn decreases the thermal stability of the remaining poly(acrylate) network, seen from the broadening towards lower temperatures of the second step. The degradation profiles of LPFG and JEFF formulations were very similar (not shown).

The thermal behaviour observed is related fundamentally with the different stability of C-N and C-C bonds, additionally, it must be considered the contribution of crosslinking density of the materials. In order to visualize this contribution on thermal degradation of the final materials, in Table 3.4 is shown the decomposition temperature for a loss mass of 5% and the maximum degradation temperature for all formulations containing LPFG, DETA and JEFF. It can be appreciated that amine-poor samples display a higher temperature value to degrade 5% of material compared with amine-rich formulations. Likewise, some trends appear when compared LPFG,

DETA and JEFF formulations for a specific N-H/acrylate ratio, those containing LPFG have higher values of $T_{5\%}$ and those containing JEFF present the lower ones, according to the higher degree of crosslinking of LPFG formulations (together with the presence of unreacted secondary amines). While, the maximum decomposition temperature for all formulations, increases with decreasing of N-H/acrylate ratio. As demonstrated before, formulations with higher amines proportion present a loosely crosslinked materials compared with formulations with lower ratio of amines with higher crosslinking density, hence the thermal stability differences between the materials is explained.

Table 3.4: Decomposition temperatures for a mass loss of 5% and maximum degradation temperatures of formulations containing 25% wt. of BGDA and 75% wt. of HDDA and different ratios of LPFG, DETA and JEFF to acrylate functional groups with a 3 wt% of DMPA as a photoinitiator.

Samples	N-H/acrylate ratio	$W_{\text{amine}}/W_{\text{acrylate}}$ (%)	$T_{5\%}$ (°C)	T_{max} (°C)
Neat			382	426
LPFG/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	3.2	340	424
	1:4	6.5	327	423
	1:2	12.9	256	414
	1:1	25.8	248	376
DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	2.0	329	425
	1:4	4.0	276	424
	1:2	8.0	242	419
	1:1	16.0	229	412
JEFF/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:8	5.7	308	422
	1:4	11.5	258	420
	1:2	23.0	233	270
	1:1	46.0	217	265

The materials prepared are more easily degradable than conventional acrylates and can be used in applications where the reworkability of the thermoset is necessary in order to remove the coating and recover valuable substrates [67]. The results obtained demonstrate that both stage one and stage two polymer properties can be tuned, for target applications, by simply changing the type of monomer, functionality and stoichiometric ratio. In the subsequent sections, it present some results on the influence of other parameters in the proposed dual curing methodology.

3.2 Effect of the acrylates

The objective of this part of the work is to study the influence of acrylate structure on the structure–property relationships of poly(amino ester)-poly(acrylate)s thermosets obtained via aza-Michael addition/acrylate photopolymerization dual curing. The networks are prepared with a constant ratio of N-H/acrylate 1:4 using DETA as crosslinking agent for the aza-Michael reaction

and a 3 wt.% of DMPA as photoinitiator, and systematically varying the rigidity of the acrylate structure and the crosslinking points coming from acrylates with varying weight fraction of the components on acrylate mixture, the type of acrylate and its functionality. Fundamental trends are established between the chemical structure of the network and crosslink density with the glass transition temperature and rubbery modulus.

In Table 3.5 and 3.6 are summarized some relevant results illustrating the effect of varying the relative amounts of BGDA and HDDA. It can be observed, on increasing BGDA content, the crosslinking density strongly decreases for both DETA/acrylate and neat formulations, in agreement with the lower acrylate content of BGDA (4.1 mol of C=C groups/kg) in comparison with HDDA (8.8 mol of C=C groups/kg).

Table 3.5: Acrylate conversion, aza-Michael reaction (%) reached and some properties before and after stage 1 for neat BGDA/HDDA and DETA/ BGDA/HDDA 1:4 formulations with 3 wt. % of DMPA as a photoinitiator.

Formulation	N-H / acrylate ratio	W _{amine} / W _{acrylate} (%)	T _{go} (°C)	Stage 1		
				Acrylate conversion (%)	Aza-Michael reaction (%)	T _g (°C)
BGDA25/HDDA75 (Neat)			-94.0	0	0	-94.0
BGDA50/HDDA50 (Neat)			-74.3	0	0	-74.3
BGDA75/HDDA25 (Neat)			-47.8	0	0	-47.8
DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:4	4.0	-94.0	23	92	-85.6
DETA/BGDA50/HDDA50	1:4	3.4	-75.0	25	100	-68.1
DETA/BGDA75/HDDA25	1:4	2.8	-49.4	25	100	-32.1

In general, the T_g after stages 1 and 2, increases progressively on increasing the proportion of BGDA, but not in the same way for both steps of curing. In the aza-Michael reaction BGDA and HDDA have a functionality of two, acting therefore as chain extenders, and in consequence the T_g after this reaction is controlled by the rigidity of structure and by the degree of crosslinking coming from amine. Taking into account that all the formulations compared have the same amount and type of amine, the T_g value depends primarily on the rigidity of the chain extender, hence the higher T_g of BGDA-rich formulation after aza-Michael reaction.

During the second curing stage acrylate groups has functionality four, being involved in the crosslinking process, so the T_g after this stage is controlled simultaneously by the rigidity and degree of crosslinking. In this case, both factors change T_g in opposite direction on increasing BGDA content. Thus, increasing BGDA increases the network rigidity but decreases the crosslinking density.

A further factor to be taken into consideration is the final lower degree of acrylate conversion that can be achieved in BGDA-rich formulations, as seen in Table 3.6, resulting in nearly 25% unreacted acrylate groups in the BGDA75/HDDA25 formulations. This is caused by the low mobility of bulky BGDA and to steric hindrance of C=C bonds in BGDA. It is known that high

molecular meth(acrylate) monomers, such as BGDA and others, need the addition of a low molecular meth(acrylate) diluents to reach the adequate viscosity and near complete curing [68].

Table 3.6: Acrylate conversion and some properties after stage 2 for neat BGDA/HDDA and DETA/BGDA/HDDA 1:4 formulations with 3 wt. % of DMPA as a photoinitiator.

Formulation	N-H / acrylate ratio	W _{amine} / W _{acrylate} (%)	Stage 2		
			Acrylate conversion (%)	T _{g∞} (°C)	E' <i>r</i> (MPa)
BGDA25/HDDA75 (Neat)			90	102	164
BGDA50/HDDA50 (Neat)			89	86	92
BGDA75/HDDA25 (Neat)			83	93	69
DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:4	4.0	99	56	73
DETA/BGDA50/HDDA50	1:4	3.4	88	64	58
DTA/BGDA75/HDDA25	1:4	2.8	75	67	28

In a second set of experiments, HDDA was replaced partially or totally by TMPTA, keeping constant the amount of BGDA (25% wt.) in the mixture of acrylates. Table 3.7 and Table 3.8 show some of the results obtained. The T_g after the first stage (seen in Table 3.7) and the T_g and crosslinking density after the second step (seen in Table 3.8) increase proportionally to the TMPTA content.

TMPTA can highly increase the crosslinking density in both stages of curing for a variety of reasons:

- (1) It has a higher acrylate content than HDDA (10.1 mol of C=C groups/kg versus 8.8 mol of C=C groups/kg)
- (2) It has a functionality 3 and 6 in aza-Michael and acrylate homopolymerization respectively (HDDA only 2 and 4)
- (3) TMPTA can contribute with an internal branching point that is activated providing the three-acrylate groups in the TMPTA molecule react.

In spite of the lower global acrylate conversion after the aza-Michael reaction and at the end of the dual-curing process, the higher crosslinking density induced by the presence of TMPTA dominates.

Table 3.7: Acrylate conversion, aza-Michael reaction (%) reached and some properties before and after stage 1 for BGDA/HDDA/TMPTA, DETA/ BGDA/HDDA/TMPTA 1:4 formulations and with 3 wt. % of DMPA as photoinitiator.

Formulation	N-H and acrylate ratio	$W_{\text{amine}}/ W_{\text{acrylate}}$ (%)	T_{go} (°C)	Stage 1		
				Acrylate conversion (%)	Aza-Michael reaction (%)	T_g (°C)
BGDA25/HDDA75 (Neat)			-94.0	0	0	-94.0
BGDA25/HDDA 37.5/TMPTA37.5 (Neat)			-78.2	0	0	-78.2
BGDA25/TMPTA75 (Neat)			-58.2	0	0	-58.2
DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:4	4.0	-94.0	23	92	-85.6
DETA/ BGDA25/HDDA 37.5/TMPTA37.5	1:4	4.2	-78.9	21	88	-62.5
DETA/BGDA25/TMPTA75	1:4	4.5	-59.8	20	80	-41.6

Table 3.8: Acrylate conversion and some properties after stage 2 for BGDA/HDDA/TMPTA, DETA/ BGDA/HDDA/TMPTA 1:4 formulations and with 3 wt. % of DMPA as photoinitiator.

Formulation	N-H and acrylate ratio	$W_{\text{amine}}/ W_{\text{acrylate}}$ (%)	Stage 2		
			Acrylate conversion (%)	$T_{g\infty}$ (°C)	$E'r$ (MPa)
BGDA25/HDDA75 (Neat)			90	102	164
BGDA25/HDDA 37.5/TMPTA37.5 (Neat)			83	115	246
BGDA25/TMPTA75 (Neat)			77	127	431
DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75	1:4	4.0	99	56	73
DETA/ BGDA25/HDDA 37.5/TMPTA37.5	1:4	3.4	90	76	157
DETA/BGDA25/TMPTA75	1:4	2.8	88	97	246

The thermal stability of DETA 1:4 formulations containing BGDA (25% wt.) and variable amounts of HDDA and TMPTA samples increases noticeably with increasing TMPTA content, as shown in Figure 3.7. It can be observed the higher onset temperature of mass loss for those samples with upper TMPTA content. The increase is related to the higher transition temperature and therefore superior crosslinking density of the sample by incorporating TMPTA due to the reasons aforementioned.

Figure 3.7: Thermogravimetric curves at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ under a nitrogen atmosphere of dual cured DETA 1:4 formulations with a 3 wt% of DMPA as a photoinitiator, 25% wt. of BGDA and varying the amounts of HDDA and TMPTA, indicated in the legend.

Figure 3.8 shows the DMA traces for the same set of formulations. In addition to the effects exerted by TMPTA on the density of crosslinking and T_g previously discussed (Table 3.7 and 3.8), it can be observed that the glassy modulus and the β -relaxation increase and decrease respectively on increasing the TMPTA content. This can be rationalized by the higher rigidity and cohesive energy density value of TMPTA than HDDA ($\text{CED}_{\text{TMPTA}}=798\text{ MPa}$ and $\text{CED}_{\text{HDDA}}=562\text{ MPa}$) [66]. In Figure 3.8, it is observed that the broadness of the $\tan \delta$ peak increases with the presence of TMPTA, indicating a more heterogeneous network structure, as commonly reported for highly crosslinked thermosets [1].

Figure 3.8: Storage moduli and $\tan \delta$ curves against temperature of dual cured DETA 1:4 formulations with a 3 wt% of DMPA as a photoinitiator, a 25% wt. of BGDA and different amounts of HDDA and TMPTA, indicated in the legend.

3.3 Effect of methacrylate

In order to test the use of methacrylates in the preparation of the thermosets via aza-Michael addition/meth(acrylate) photopolymerization dual curing, it was studied the complete replacement of HDDA by TEGDMA in LPFG/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:4 formulations with 3 wt.% of DMPA.

The overall acrylate/methacrylate conversion after the aza-Michael reaction was 22 % (as shown in Figure 3.9), a value close to the expected one of 25%, but it was found that the methacrylate conversion was only 9 %, while the acrylate conversion was 87 %. This result agrees with the fact that alkyl methacrylates groups are relatively poor Michael acceptors and with the steric hindrance caused by the methyl in α position [25].

Figure 3.9: Comparison between acrylate and acrylate/methacrylate conversions determined by FTIR technique at 35 °C during aza-Michael reaction of LPFG/BGDA25/TEGDMA75 1:4 and 3 wt.% DMPA.

The T_g after the aza-Michael reaction was 26°C. At the end of the curing process, the overall acrylate/methacrylate conversion was 99 %, showing only a small amount of unreacted acrylate, about 5 %. The final $T_{g\infty}$ was of 150°C, with a relaxed modulus E'_r of 83 MPa. Comparing these results with those obtained previously with LPFG/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:4 formulation (see Table 3.1), some differences can be observed when TEGDMA is used:

- (1) During stage 1, C=C bonds react and aza-Michael takes places in a higher extension, but most of the double bonds reacted are acrylates coming from BGDA. As a consequence, the glass transition temperature raises further, since the rigid BGDA is mainly incorporated to the structure instead of the more flexible TEGDMA backbone since they act as chain extenders.
- (2) During stage 2, acrylate and methacrylate conversions are practically complete, remaining a small amount of unreacted acrylates in both cases.
- (3) The mobility of homopolymerized poly(methacrylate) chains is much lower than those of homopolymerized poly(acrylate) chains, because of the further chain rotational barrier caused by the presence of the side methyl moieties in the repeating units along the chain. Hence the much higher T_g obtained with TEGDMA after the second curing process.

Methacrylate/acrylate mixtures may be suitable for dual curing consisting of a self-limiting click aza-Michael addition followed by acrylate/meth(acrylate) homopolymerization. However, it is difficult to anticipate the intermediate and final properties of the materials because:

- (1) The different reactivity of both unsaturated monomers, especially during aza-Michael addition
- (2) Their different contribution, in terms of network structure and mobility, after the aza-Michael reaction and the subsequent acrylate/methacrylate homopolymerization.

Given the above results, one can hypothesize that the network characteristics after the aza-Michael reaction will be determined by the structure of acrylate used, but the final network will depend fundamentally on the methacrylate structure and on the relative amount of acrylate/methacrylate.

3.4 Effect of different types of initiators

Type II photoinitiators are photoreactive substances that require a co-initiator or synergist to produce initiating radicals. This kind of photoinitiator forms an excited state upon irradiation and then abstracts an atom or electron from a donor molecule (co-initiator). The donor molecule then acts as the initiating species of polymerization. A widely used Type II photoinitiator consists in benzophenone in combination with tertiary amines. Tertiary amines are typically used as co-initiator, because they react efficiently with benzophenone (BENP) and also act as oxygen scavengers [8].

It was firstly tested 3% of BENP as photoinitiator of neat BGDA25/HDDA75 acrylate formulation. As expected, the curing process did not take place and almost all C=C bonds remained unreacted even after 20 minutes of irradiation. The results were completely different when a 3% of BENP was used in DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:2 formulations and equivalent to those obtained for this same formulation using a 3% DMPA (Table 3.1). In general, properties and conversion after the two stages of curing were practically the same for both photoinitiators and only a slight increase of conversion velocity at the beginning of the aza-Michael addition was observed using BENP (seen in Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10: Comparison between the use of DMPA and DEMP in acrylate conversions determined by FTIR technique at 35 °C during aza-Michael reaction of DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:2 formulation.

Figure 3.11 shows the dynamic mechanical relaxation spectra for DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:2 formulations obtained using DMPA or benzophenone (BENP) as photoinitiators. As we can see, both materials have similar properties after dual curing.

Figure 3.11: Storage moduli and $\tan \delta$ curves against temperature of dual cured DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:2 formulations with 3 % of DMPA and 3 % of benzophenone as a photoinitiator.

It must also be accentuated that BENP is active as photoinitiator in the presence of DETA, allowing acrylate groups to achieve near complete photocuring during the second stage. Since DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:2 formulation does not content tertiary amines or other hydrogen donor that can act as co-initiator, the tertiary amines formed during aza-Michael addition should be the responsible for the observed behaviour [8].

Moreover, in some applications where UV-irradiation is not available, the thermal activation of the second curing stage may be useful. As a proof of concept a LPFG/BGDA25/TMPTA75 1:4 formulation containing 3 wt. % of methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) and 0.1% of cobalt(II) octoate (OCO) as thermal initiator and promotor respectively, were cured according to the following curing schedule: 3 h at 35°C (aza-Michael addition) followed by a sequence of isothermal curing stages with increasing temperatures to reach the maximum curing. It was verified, in an amine-free formulation, that the radical initiating system was stable at 35 °C for 3 hours.

LPFG and TMPTA were used in this test, instead of DETA and HDDA, because of the low boiling temperature of HDDA and DETA, which prevented its use in thermal curing formulations. After the aza-Michael addition reaction, acrylate conversion of 20 % was achieved (equivalent to 80% of aza-Michael addition), and in the subsequent stepped thermal curing sequence acrylate conversion increased to 64% after 60 min at 150°C, to 84% after 120 min more at 180°C and 92 % after 30 min at 200 °C. After this curing schedule, DMA analysis showed a T_g of 100 °C that increased up to 150 °C after a second DMA scan (as seen in Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.12: Storage moduli and $\tan \delta$ curves against temperature of dual cured DETA/BGDA25/HDDA75 1:2 formulations with 3 % of MEKP as thermal initiator and 0.1% OCO as promotor after two DMA scan.

Benzoyl peroxide (BPOX) was tested as thermal initiator as well, the results obtained were equivalent than those obtained with MEKP, and however, the materials had defects due to formation of carbon dioxide during thermal curing. It can be concluded that poly(amino ester)-poly(acrylate)s thermosets with nearly complete cure can be obtained by thermal activation of the second curing stage, being the energetic cost of the process and the evaporation of the monomers the only limiting factor.

4. Conclusions

In this thesis project, it has been prepared via novel dual-curing solvent-free process at ambient temperature a new set of poly(amino ester)-poly(acrylate)s thermosets based on off-stoichiometric amine-acrylate formulations. The first stage of curing consists in a self-limiting aza-Michael addition between amine and acrylate groups and the second stage is an acrylate radical photopolymerization of the excess of acrylates.

The novel dual methodology is very versatile and allows tuning, the mechanical and thermal properties of the prepared materials after both stages of curing with an adequate selection of the monomers and the stoichiometry of the formulations. The obtained materials can be gelled or ungelled and safely stored after the first curing stage, and loosely or tightly crosslinked at the end of the second curing stage. The flexibility of the methodology proposed is based in the orthogonality of both stages of curing since the excess of acrylate groups are not able of homopolymerizing during aza-Michael addition at ambient temperature.

The presence of tertiary amines formed during aza-Michael addition overcomes the intrinsic oxygen inhibition of acrylate free-radical polymerizations and allows the curing to be performed in non-inert environments. Type II photoinitiators can be used to promote the radical homopolymerization of acrylates because of the tertiary amines act as co-initiator.

By selecting adequately a free-radical thermal initiator and the temperature and time of reaction, the second stage of curing can be activated thermally, keeping the orthogonality both curing stages.

5. Bibliography

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